
PARENTAL MOTIVATION AND ITS INFLUENCE ON EFL/ESL LEARNING: A REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

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Abstract: This paper reviews the existing research on the role of parental motivation in enhancing the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and English as a Second Language (ESL) learning process. It explores the concept of motivation, its different types, and how parental attitudes and behaviors can significantly impact a child's motivation and ultimately, their success in learning English.

Keywords: Parental Motivation, EFL/ESL Learning, Second Language Acquisition, Student Motivation.

Introduction

Motivation is a well-established factor influencing success in second language acquisition [3]. In the context of EFL/ESL learning, parental motivation plays a crucial role in fostering a child's interest and engagement with the language. This review examines the various ways parental motivation can influence the EFL/ESL learning process. Parental motivation in EFL/ESL learning is a topic of increasing importance due to several factors:

- **Globalization:** The growing interconnectedness of the world makes English proficiency valuable for education, career prospects, and communication.
- **Focus on Early Language Learning:** Many countries are starting English language instruction at younger ages, making parental support crucial from the beginning.
- **Diversity in Parental Backgrounds:** With increasing immigration and cultural exchange, parents may have varying levels of English proficiency or cultural understanding of EFL/ESL learning.

Despite its recognized importance, there's still room for further research in this area:

- **Culturally Specific Strategies:** A deeper understanding of how parents from different cultural backgrounds motivate their children can lead to more effective strategies.
- **Teacher-Parent Collaboration:** Research can explore how teachers and schools can better collaborate with parents to create a unified and supportive learning environment.
- **Impact on Different Age Groups:** The ways parents motivate younger and older learners might differ, and research can identify effective strategies for each age group.

Understanding parental motivation is crucial for maximizing the success of EFL/ESL programs. By providing targeted support and fostering collaboration between parents, teachers, and researchers, we can create a more effective and engaging learning environment for all students.

Research suggests two main types of parental motivation that impact EFL/ESL learning:

- **Instrumental Motivation:** This refers to parents' focus on the practical benefits of learning English, such as future career opportunities or academic success [2]. Instrumental motivation refers to a practical or goal-oriented approach to learning English. Parents with instrumental motivation focus on the external benefits their child will gain from mastering English, such as better job opportunities, higher grades, or simply fulfilling a school requirement. They see English as a tool that unlocks future success in other areas.

Integrative Motivation: This reflects a desire for the child to connect with the culture and people associated with the English language [2]. Integrative motivation delves deeper than simply acquiring English as a tool. It reflects a genuine desire for the child to connect with the culture and people associated with the English language. Here's a more detailed breakdown:

- **Cultural Connection:** Parents with integrative motivation want their child to appreciate the richness and diversity of English-speaking cultures. This might involve encouraging them to explore English literature, music, movies, or traditions.

- **Building Relationships:** They see English as a bridge that allows their child to connect and build friendships with people from different backgrounds. This fosters a sense of global citizenship and understanding.

- **Identity and Belonging:** In some cases, integrative motivation might stem from a desire for the child to feel a sense of belonging within an English-speaking community, particularly if they live in a multilingual environment.

Integrative motivation goes beyond just achieving a certain grade or test score. It's about fostering a lifelong interest in the language and the cultures it represents. This intrinsic desire to connect can be a powerful driver for language acquisition, encouraging children to engage with English beyond the classroom setting.

Parental Behaviors and their Impact: Parents can express their motivation through various behaviors:

- **Positive Attitude:** Parents who express a positive view of English and its importance can influence their child's perception and motivation [1].

- **Creating a Language-Rich Environment:** Surrounding children with English through books, music, and movies exposes them to the language in a natural way [5].

- **Engaging with Learning:** Parents who participate in their child's learning by helping with homework or discussing English topics can show their support and increase engagement [4].

Challenges and Considerations: While parental motivation is significant, it's important to consider potential challenges:

Pressure and Anxiety: Overly ambitious parental expectations can create pressure and anxiety, hindering the learning process [1]. While parental motivation can be a powerful tool for boosting a child's EFL/ESL learning, there's a fine line to tread. Overly ambitious expectations from parents can backfire, creating pressure and anxiety that hinder the learning process. Here's how this can happen:

When parents set unrealistic goals or constantly compare their child's progress to others, it can create a fear of failure in the child. This fear can paralyze them, making them hesitant to participate in class or take risks with the language, ultimately hindering their learning. When the emphasis is solely on achieving top grades or perfect scores on tests, the joy of learning itself gets lost. This can lead to rote memorization and a lack of genuine understanding or interest in the language.

The pressure to perform well in front of parents or teachers can trigger performance anxiety, making the child freeze up or struggle to recall what they've learned. This can be particularly detrimental in situations where speaking and interacting in English are crucial. Constant criticism or negativity from parents can erode a child's confidence in their ability to learn English. This can lead to a self-fulfilling prophecy, where the child believes they're not good at the language and stops trying altogether.

It's important for parents to strike a balance between encouraging their child and creating a supportive environment that fosters a love of learning. Focusing on progress, celebrating small victories, and emphasizing the importance of communication over perfect grammar can go a long way in mitigating pressure and anxiety.

- **Limited Resources or Knowledge:** Parents with limited English proficiency or resources might struggle to support their child's learning directly [5].

Conclusion

Parental motivation is a critical factor influencing children's success in learning EFL/ESL. By fostering a positive attitude, creating a language-rich environment, and engaging with their child's learning journey, parents can significantly contribute to their child's motivation and ultimately, their language acquisition. In conclusion, parental motivation plays a critical role in shaping a child's EFL/ESL learning journey. By fostering a positive attitude towards English, creating a language-rich environment, and actively engaging with their child's learning, parents can significantly contribute to their child's success. Understanding the different types of motivation, instrumental and integrative, allows parents to tailor their approach and nurture a genuine interest in

the language. However, it's crucial to avoid creating undue pressure or anxiety through unrealistic expectations. By striking a balance between encouragement and support, parents can empower their children to embrace the challenges and joys of learning English, ultimately propelling them towards fluency and a deeper connection with the wider world. As research in this area continues to evolve, with a focus on culturally specific strategies and teacher-parent collaboration, we can create a more effective and engaging learning environment for all EFL/ESL students.

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